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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF UNIVERSAL COMPETENCIES OF STUDENTS

Bakhtiyor Suvonkulov

Jizzakh State Pedagogical University named after ...
 PhD, Associate Professor

Abstract: In order to more comprehensively conceptualize the graduate model of higher education, it is necessary to specify the structure and content of general, professional, and universal competencies. It is also crucial to highlight the significance of universal competencies in relation to social and cultural requirements, independent evaluation of students' educational outcomes, and their close interconnection with cultural competencies.

Key words: method, methodology, educational-cognitive activity, activity, competence, communication, education, upbringing, universal, teacher, student.

Annotatsiya: Uzluksiz ta'lim tizimida bitiruvchi modelini yanada kengroq tasavvur qilish uchun umumiy, kasbiy va universal kompetensiyalarning tarkibi hamda mazmunini aniqlashtirish zarur. Shu bilan birga, universal kompetensiyalarning ijtimoiy va madaniy talablar asosidagi vazifalarini, talabalarning ta'limiy faoliyat natijalarini mustaqil baholash imkoniyatlarini, madaniy kompetensiyalar bilan o'zaro bog'liqligini ko'rsatish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: metod, metodologiya, ta'lim-kognitiv faoliyat, faoliyat, kompetensiya, kommunikatsiya, ta'lim, tarbiya, universal, o'qituvchi, talaba.

Аннотация: Для более широкого представления модели выпускника системы высшего образования необходимо уточнить состав и содержание общих, профессиональных и универсальных компетенций. Важно также определить значимость универсальных компетенций в выполнении социальных и культурных задач, самостоятельной оценке результатов учебной деятельности студентов, а также в тесной связи с культурными компетенциями.

Ключевые слова: метод, методология, учебно-познавательная деятельность, деятельность, компетенция, коммуникация, образование, воспитание, универсальные компетенции, преподаватель, студент.

INTRODUCTION

Engineering education throughout the world is at the stage of innovative development, and these changes are associated with the transition to an information society and the introduction of new types of activities. In determining the goals and results of training specialists in the field of construction, due to the change in the objectives of modern engineering education, the need to increase the general culture of specialists has become evident. Researchers are increasingly focusing on the general cultural competencies of graduates.

This issue is determined by the role of personnel in the construction industry in ensuring the development and well-being of society. A feature of modernised society is the formation of new production paradigms. This paradigm, in turn, has led to the need for professionals with a high level of culture (communication, ability to work in a team, etc.). Practice shows that professional training improves significantly with the integration of social, cultural, and personal competencies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the study and analysis of the theoretical foundations of the development of the universal competency of students, the concepts "culture", "competence", "cultural competence", and "universal competence" were analyzed. Culture ^[6] is defined as a set of achievements in the production, social, spiritual, and educational life of society; the level of such achievements that a social group, class, or people have attained in a certain period; literacy, education, intellectual, and enlightenment. According to the Qomusian Dictionary of Philosophy, the word "culture" refers to education and is argued to be a specific way of human activity, which is reflected in

relationships. Culture reflects the life activity (personal culture) of an individual and the lifestyle of a social group or society. Culture is the process of human activity and the spiritual values created as a result, which in turn is a social phenomenon considered an important factor in the formation and maturation of an individual ^[4].

Culture is a rich and complex phenomenon. It is manifested in all aspects of human life activity. The interpretation of this social phenomenon, which plays a positive role in the development process of culture, should be supplemented by two additional approaches. The first is manifested in the understanding of the positive process of cultural activity, and the second is a specific way of human activity. General interpretations of cultural activities are common, but the methods of explanation are often not identical ^[6]. The phenomenon of "culture" envisages the existence of a complex multidimensional phenomenon ^[3]. Culture is the mechanism by which an individual enters into social life, achieves self-awareness, and perceives uniqueness from others. Culture encompasses the ability to apply experiences accumulated by humanity ^[4].

The essence of culture is manifested not in the sum of achievements and values accumulated by mankind in the process of historical progress, but in activity itself. In each element of culture, four functional qualities are distinguished: knowledge, feelings or attitudes, motivation, and actions. The main social function of culture is human creativity ^[2]. Culture, as a complex phenomenon, is reflected in all aspects of life activity. To understand its positive role in development, it must be analyzed both as an activity and as a specific way of human practice. However, the methods of defining cultural activity often differ ^[5].

The study of culture is expressed in two directions: in the context of personality development ^[2] and as a universal property of social life ^[1]. These views are actively used in the literature in understanding the essence of culture ^[2]. In psychological and pedagogical literature, culture is regarded as a historically established level of society, creative forces, and human abilities, expressed in the forms of organization of people's lives and activities, their relationships, and in material aspects.

Human spirituality is the most fundamental criterion that determines and realizes the needs and interests of a person and manifests the essence of his activity aimed at protecting or satisfying them. For this reason, in the formation of a harmonious personality, it is essential to correctly assess the proportionality between spirituality, needs, and interests, and to balance material requirements with high standards of spirituality. Culture encourages continuous development. Systems of sequential rules, in which activity is passed from generation to generation in a holistic way, constitute the technology of activity that forms the essence of culture.

Culture, as a mode of activity, is an open system involving dynamic rather than closed algorithms, which reshape and adjust the energy of human action. This energy is impossible without real cultural and historical creativity. Formative activity induces constructive (creative) activity. A lower level of culture reflects passive adaptation to existence, while the higher level represents the creation of one's own world, which absorbs external factors yet resists them with originality ^[3].

- Culture – a certain level of organization of human life expressed in the products of material and spiritual creativity, in the mastery of techniques and methods of labor, mental activity, and the pursuit of physical and spiritual perfection.
- Culture is not an independent social sphere but an interconnected aspect of the entire social system, present in every social phenomenon.
- Culture is an important feature of individuals, groups, social, professional, and national communities, and society as a whole.
- The essence of culture is manifested not in the sum of accumulated achievements but in activity itself.

It is also necessary to characterize the concept of specialist culture, which is formed and developed in students as future professionals ^[5]. Specialist culture enables individuals to meet social requirements, solve professional problems meaningfully, be proficient in advanced technologies, and act in accordance with the pace of societal development while recognizing universal priorities ^[7].

In the course of the study, it was found that the universal competency of students is closely related to their cultural literacy. In describing cultural literacy, E.D. Hirsch's works are noteworthy. Hirsch argued that educators often lose the ability to communicate and understand one another because they lack common reference points and are unfamiliar with essential facts. This makes them culturally illiterate, meaning they do not know key aspects of different cultures. Hirsch concluded that cultural commonality is necessary to ensure effective communication between people, and this commonality must be built upon universally shared concepts. He also emphasized that the content of education should be organized around these concepts.

Thus, students must be able to freely use common concepts during communication. This set of concepts should form the foundation of educational content, which, as Hirsch believed, ensures cultural literacy and effective communication among individuals ^[4].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Methodological foundations for the development of universal competencies of students were, in general, analyzed through regulatory documents to clarify the methodological basis of the study. In particular, in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 2017-04-20, PQ-2909 "On measures for the further development of the higher education system", tasks such as the prevention of information threats against the consciousness of student youth, the formation of a culture of proper use of information, the Internet and other information resources, the creation and maintenance of a healthy spiritual and moral climate (mutual respect in the community, culture of treatment, etc.), the organization of meaningful recreation of students in their free time, the formation of a healthy lifestyle, the development of respect and love for books, and the reading culture of students, as well as the enhancement of their legal knowledge and legal culture, were defined. Within the framework of these tasks, the main focus is on the formation and development of the culture of students.

In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 2019-10-08, PF-5847 "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", particular attention was paid to raising awareness of the essence of legislation among young people, the development of legal consciousness and culture, compliance with a healthy lifestyle, human rights, gender equality, pacifism and interethnic harmony, freedom of conscience, perfection of national-moral values along with universal values such as respect for the languages, customs, and traditions of all nations, socio-political and economic activity, and the formation of civic culture.

Attention was also paid to the issues of forming a culture of information analysis among students, developing a plan of spiritual and educational measures to foster love for the motherland and its destiny, nurturing dedication, and ensuring the implementation of these measures in all higher educational institutions. According to international criteria, the main requirements for the quality of education in undergraduate programs in technical areas include professional competencies, awareness of the social and political consequences of engineering decisions, the application of methods studied in engineering practice, problem-solving, effective teamwork, and the ability to engage in lifelong learning.

In international research, particular importance is given to requirements such as knowledge of engineering disciplines, engineering analysis, design and engineering solutions development, research, use of modern tools, ethics, and teamwork^[6]. In a number of research projects, the results are explained in detail, making it clear what knowledge and skills students who have completed engineering education programs should possess. At the same time, personal and interpersonal competencies are also emphasized. Individual competencies determine the cognitive and affective development of each graduate, which are manifested in technical thinking, problem-solving ability, the desire to discover and invent new ideas, as well as creative and critical thinking.

Interpersonal competencies, on the other hand, include the graduate's ability to work independently and in a team, leadership qualities, and the ability to communicate effectively in a group^[1]. Thus, at each stage of societal development, certain requirements are imposed on graduates of higher education. In particular, graduates are required to develop and demonstrate universal competencies.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Analysis shows that the requirements for bachelors in technical fields are enhanced by personal and social competencies, which share common cultural characteristics. It should be noted that experiments in the United States and European countries demonstrate that the issue of forming general competencies among bachelors of technical orientation arose mainly from the processes of integrating graduates into the global social and cultural environment in the second half of the 20th century. A feature of post-industrial society is the formation of new production paradigms that include non-material resources such as knowledge, information, and communication.

The new production paradigm led to the need for professionals with a high level of culture (communication, self-realization, independence, responsibility, ability to work in a team, etc.). The task of modern engineering and technical universities is to train such specialists. In this context, in the process of preparing bachelors of technical orientation in Western Europe and America, professional competencies are complemented by social, cultural, and personal competencies, which are referred to as "basic competencies." These competencies are universal, that is, cultural in nature.

In general, during the professional training of students in engineering education, international educational experiments pay great attention to the humanities as well as the development of personal qualities. Students are capable of applying learned methods, formulating and solving problems, engaging in lifelong learning, working in a team, being responsible, and demonstrating erudition. These qualities are defined as general cultural competencies, as they reflect the overall culture of the professional in the field of engineering. In broader terms, the universal competency of future engineers is thereby reflected.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

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